

Thermal analysis of phenoxyacetic acids of bisphenol derivatives and poly(*R,R',4,4'*-cyclohexylidenediphenylene phosphorochloridate)

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DTA-TG thermograms of phenoxyacetic acid derivatives of bisphenol-S, phenolphthalein and polyphosphates of bisphenol-C derivatives have been scanned. PAAS-1 to -4 and PAAP-1 to -4 are thermally stable up to 291–336° and 306–331°, respectively, and involved two-step decomposition. PHO-1 to -6 are thermally stable up to 212–302° and followed either single or two-step degradation. The DTA transitions support either some physical change or chemical change. The kinetic parameters are interpreted in light of the nature of the substituents (CH₃, Cl, Br and NO₂). A large and positive ΔS^\ddagger suggests less ordered transition state while negative ΔS^\ddagger supports ordered transition state.

Phenoxy acids are widely helpful in the field of agriculture as herbicides as well as insecticides¹. Organophosphorus ester resins are used as additive in gasoline and plastic materials, plasticizers and fire retardant^{2,3}. A literature survey revealed no work on thermal analysis of phenoxyacetic acids of phenolphthalein and bisphenol-S as well as polyphosphates of bisphenol-C. The present work reports thermal behavior of phenoxyacetic acids of phenolphthalein derivatives and bisphenol-S (I) and polyphosphates of bisphenol-C derivatives (II).

Z = Phthalide	Z = SO ₂
PAAP-1 : R = R' = H	PAAS-1 : R = R' = H
PAAP-2 : R = R' = Cl	PAAS-2 : R = R' = Cl
PAAP-3 : R = R' = Br	PAAS-3 : R = R' = Br
PAAP-4 : R = R' = NO ₂	PAAS-4 : R = R' = NO ₂

PHO-1 : R = R' = H	PHO-4 : R = CH ₃ , R' = Cl
PHO-2 : R = CH ₃ , R' = H	PHO-5 : R = R' = Br
PHO-3 : R = R' = Cl	PHO-6 : R = CH ₃ , R' = Br

Results and Discussion

In order to understand the nature of the substituents on kinetics of thermal degradation of PAAS-1 to -4, PAAP-1 to -4 and PHO-1 and -6, DTA-TG, thermograms were scanned. The DTA transitions along with the initial decomposition temperature (IDT), the decomposition temperature range, temperature of maximum weight-loss (T_{max}) and percent weight-loss for a given step are reported in Tables 1 and 2. The results reveal that exothermic transition(s) is/are due to the rupture of the phenoxy acetic acids or new compounds formed as a result of decomposition as supported by TG data over this temperature and the endothermic transition(s) due to some physical change as supported by no weight-loss over this temperature range in corresponding TG thermograms.

Energy of activation (E_a), order of the reaction (n) and frequency factor (A) are dominant factors in deciding the shape of the TG thermograms. PAAS-1 to -4 are thermally stable up to 291–336° and involve two-step decomposition. The observed thermal stability order is PAAS-2 > PAAS-1 > PAAS-3 > PAAS-4. The first step involved weight-loss of about 35–49% while the second step involved about 28–39% weight-loss leaving about 8% residual weight. From Table 1, it is observed that the nature of the substituents (Cl, Br and NO₂) not only affects IDT but also T_{max} .

PAAP-1 to -4 are thermally stable up to about 306–331°, involving two-step decomposition. The observed thermal stability order is PAAP-2 > PAAP-4 > PAAP-1 = PAAP-3. The first step involved weight-loss of about 35–43% except PAAP-2 (~19%) while second step involved

Table 1. TG-DTA data of the phenoxy acids

Phenoxy acid	Transition	Temp. °C	IDT °C	Decom. range °C	% Wt. loss	T_{max} °C	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	A s ⁻¹	ΔS^* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	n	γ
PAAS-1	Exo	333.7	315.2	315–371	35.3	353.7	96.1	7.53×10^5	-138.6	0.45	0.966
	Exo	554.0	506.5	507–564	39.3	548.0	270.0	1.73×10^{15}	38.8	1.71	0.999
	Exo	335.7									
PAAS-2	Exo	531.3	324.7	325–363	38.8	350.6	272.7	1.47×10^{21}	154.2	1.07	0.952
	Endo	638.1	477.6	478–564	39.4	532.0	113.8	1.28×10^5	-155.4	1.24	0.981
	Endo	291.3									
PAAS-3	Exo	572.8	304.8	305–353	46.5	330.4	222.7	3.47×10^{17}	85.0	1.63	0.988
	Exo	666.1	536.4	536–594	34.0	567.2	581.2	3.33×10^{34}	407.4	3.73	0.999
	Endo	163.9									
PAAS-4	Exo	276.0									
	Exo	532.3	291.0	291–324	49.2	316.4	207.2	4.11×10^{16}	67.5	0.90	0.992
	Exo	620.3	483.0	483–554	28.0	530.6	191.8	2.61×10^{10}	-53.7	0.88	0.988
PAAP-1	Exo	664.8									
	Endo	259.4	305.7	306–363	34.5	342.5	157.8	3.09×10^{11}	-31.0	1.42	0.991
	Exo	547.3	502.7	503–576	49.1	535.3	204.7	1.60×10^{11}	-38.7	1.62	0.996
PAAP-2	Exo	283.4									
	Exo	537.5	331.4	331–379	18.9	363.1	216.8	1.03×10^{16}	55.3	1.56	0.926
	Exo	669.0	490.5	491–560	56.8	519.3	362.7	1.41×10^{22}	171.0	2.36	0.997
PAAP-3	Exo	556.6	305.7	306–360	42.9	342.9	138.6	6.25×10^9	-63.4	1.47	0.995
PAAP-4	Endo	263.7	523.9	524–575	33.0	554.1	692.6	1.67×10^{42}	554.9	3.96	0.996
	Exo	360.8	324.0	324–374	39.6	355.7	133.8	1.33×10^9	-76.5	1.28	0.972
	Exo	624.5	570.0	570–647	44.3	619.2	529.4	1.97×10^{29}	306.8	4.46	0.994

weight-loss of about 44–57% except PAAP-3 (33%) and left about 10% residual weight in each case. The chlorine and nitro groups have increased thermal stability and T_{max} to small extent. The bromine substituent has not affected the said parameters (Table 1).

From Table 2, it is observed that PHO-1, PHO-3 and PHO-5 follow single step degradation while PHO-2, PHO-4 and PHO-6 follow two-step degradation. The results reveal

that polyphosphates are thermally stable up to about 240–255° except PHO-5 (212°) and PHO-6 (302°). PHO-2 and PHO-4 showed a complex degradation pattern. The observed thermal stability order is PHO-6 > PHO-3 > PHO-1 > PHO-2 ≈ PHO-4 > PHO-5. The methyl substituent lowered thermal stability to a small extent but chlorine substituent has a little effect on thermal stability. The bromine substituent has affected thermal stability to a considerable

Table 2. TG-DTA data of the polyphosphates

Poly-phosphate	Transition	Temp. °C	IDT °C	Decon. range, °C	% wt. loss	T_{max} °C	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	A s ⁻¹	ΔS^* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	n	γ
PHO-1	Endo	183.3									
	Endo	290.6	250	250–295	82	290.6	400.7	5.22×10^{35}	433.6	0.10	0.985
	Exo	547.6									
PHO-2	Endo	256.5									
	Exo	544.0	241	241–270	33	249.6	21.0	0.29	-259.9	1.12	0.957
	Exo	660.4		312–452	28	432.3	-	-	-	-	-
PHO-3	Endo	181.0									
	Endo	308.7	255	255–316	89	308.2	157.2	1.89×10^{12}	-15.4	0.53	0.992
	Exo	78.2									
PHO-4	Endo	255.7									
	Exo	335.6	240	240–280	40	253.3	13.8	3.44×10^{-2}	-173.4	0.12	0.929
	Endo	417.5	280	280–430	30	315.0	318.8	5.81×10^{26}	261.8	8.59	0.958
PHO-5	Exo	547.8									
	Endo	633.7									
	Endo	242.5									
PHO-6	Endo	365.3	212	212–276	74	240.3	91.5	2.12×10^7	-109.2	1.23	0.963
	Exo	541.7									
	Exo	554.2	302	302–395	46	334.2	37.8	5.51	-236.6	0.32	0.945
PHO-6	Exo	671.2	544	544–583	6	549.1	-	-	-	-	-
	Exo	708.1									

extent. PHO-1 to -6 possess a considerably better thermal stability as compared to polyphosphate of bisphenol-A³ (~180°) indicating enhancement of thermal stability due to a cyclohexyl group in the main chain.

In order to evaluate kinetic parameters, the method of the Freeman-Anderson⁴ was adopted. The least-square kinetic parameters along with correlation coefficients are reported in Tables 1 and 2. The frequency factor (A) and the entropy change (ΔS^*) for a given step are determined at T_{\max} . High magnitudes of activation energy and order of the reaction (n) are indicative of rigid and complex nature of the degradation reaction especially for the second step probably due to interference of degradation of side substituents and new compounds formed.

The ether and phosphate linkages, and side substituents (CH_3 , Cl, Br and NO_2) are weak points in the molecules, which degrade selectively, and radicals may form. These radicals may further recombine to form new product(s) as evident in DTA thermograms. These new product(s) may further degrade at higher temperatures resulting in low molecular weight products. The degradation process is a complex process, which involves a variety of reactions. A large and positive magnitudes of ΔS^* confirm that the transition state is less ordered than individual original molecules while negative values suggest ordered transition state.

On the basis of the experimental findings, it is concluded that the nature of the substituents has affected both thermal stability and T_{\max} to some extent. DTA transitions supported either decomposition or some physical change. PAAS-1 to -4 and PAAP-1 to -4 followed two-step decomposition, while PHO-1 to -6 followed either one-step or two-step degradation.

Experimental

Phenoxyacetic acids of phenolphthalein derivatives (PAAP-1 to -4) and bisphenol-S (PAAS-1 to -4) derivatives were synthesized by condensing the corresponding phenolphthalein and bisphenol-S derivatives with chloroacetic acid in the presence of sodium hydroxide at reflux temperature for 4 h. The compounds were crystallized from MeOH-H₂O system. Polyphosphates (PHO-1 to -6) were synthesized by condensing the corresponding bisphenol-C derivatives with POCl_3 using pyridine as a catalyst at 95° for 4 h and at 240° for 6 h. The compounds were crystallized from DMF-H₂O system. The samples used were oligomeric in nature having solution viscosity of 1.07–1.17 Pas for 1.25% at 30°. DTA-TG thermograms of PAAP-1 to -4, PAAS-1 to -4 and PHO-1 to -6 were scanned on a Mettler TS system at a heating rate of 15°/min in nitrogen atmosphere.

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